

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document details the MARINEWIND survey, including the methodology for its creation, the data to be collected, and the intended use of this data. Floating Offshore Wind Technology (FOWT) is expected to play a significant role in the global energy transition. Despite this potential, the technology is still in its early stages, with only a few prototypes and pre-commercial offshore wind farms operating worldwide. This limited deployment leads to uncertainty among various socio-economic sectors, including fisheries, tourism, and local communities in areas where FOWTs may be installed.

The MARINEWIND survey is designed to gather comprehensive data to tackle the uncertainties surrounding the FOWT energy sector focusing on several key areas such as policy making, social acceptance, environmental impact, financial and market analysis, and techno-economic analysis. Each section of the survey targets specific objectives and questions to capture stakeholder perceptions, potential barriers, enablers, and strategies for mitigating conflicts.

Policy-making: This section explores the involvement of government entities in fostering FOWT, the extent to which stakeholders are involved in the consenting process and the impact of stakeholder engagement on the perception of FOWT projects. Questions focus on the extent to which stakeholders are involved in decision-making processes, the transparency of these processes, and the effectiveness of government policies in promoting FOWT deployment. The data collected will help identify best practices for fostering positive stakeholder relationships and enhancing policy frameworks.

Social Acceptance: This part of the survey seeks to understand the level of awareness and acceptance of FOWT among different sectors, including local communities, fisheries, and tourism industries. It addresses perceptions of FOWT benefits and drawbacks, the level of trust in developers and authorities, and the effectiveness of communication strategies. By identifying socio-economic barriers and enablers, the survey aims to propose strategies to enhance public understanding and acceptance, thereby reducing social conflicts and fostering a more supportive environment for FOWT projects.

Environmental Impact: Questions in this section focus on assessing stakeholders' views on the environmental implications of FOWT deployment, including potential impacts on marine life, seabirds, and coastal ecosystems. The survey also explores perceptions of the environmental benefits of FOWTs, such as reduced greenhouse gas emissions and the potential for habitat creation. The goal is to balance development with ecological sustainability, ensuring that environmental considerations are integrated into project planning and implementation.

Techno-Economic Analysis: This part evaluates the technological and economic feasibility of FOWT projects, assessing factors such as technology readiness levels, cost efficiency, and potential market expansion opportunities. Questions cover the perceived advantages and disadvantages of different FOWT technologies, the potential for cost reductions through

technological advancements, and the scalability of FOWT solutions. The insights gained will help in developing strategies to improve the competitiveness and feasibility of FOWT as a mainstream renewable energy source.

Financial and Market Analysis: This section addresses financial perceptions, barriers, and enablers related to FOWT investments. It includes questions on the perceived financial viability of FOWT projects, the availability of funding and subsidies, and the risks associated with investing in this emerging technology. The survey will analyse key financial metrics such as the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), Return on Investment (ROI), and payback periods to identify strategies for attracting investment and fostering market growth.

The collected data will be analysed to identify trends, common opinions, and correlations between stakeholders' views and various factors such as nationality, professional roles, and environmental awareness. The insights gained will inform strategies to enhance the deployment and acceptance of FOWT, contributing to the broader goals of energy transition and sustainability.

2. INTRODUCTION

The MARINEWIND project is a forward-looking initiative co-funded by the EU commission program. Its primary goal is to promote the market uptake of FOWTs. This document serves as a comprehensive overview of the MARINEWIND survey, detailing the methodology used to create the survey, the specific data to be collected, and the intended applications of this data.

Purpose of the Document

The primary purpose of this document is to provide stakeholders with a thorough understanding of the MARINEWIND survey. It outlines the rationale behind the survey's design, the types of questions included, and the methodologies employed to ensure robust and meaningful data collection. Additionally, the document aims to illustrate how the collected data will be used to address key challenges and opportunities associated with FOWT deployment.

Floating Offshore Wind Technology represents a significant advancement in renewable energy, offering the potential to harness wind resources in deeper waters where traditional fixed-bottom turbines are not feasible. However, the deployment of FOWT is still in its early stages, with only a few prototypes and pre-commercial projects worldwide. This limited experience generates uncertainties and challenges that the MARINEWIND survey seeks to address. The survey covers several critical areas of focus:

Policymaking: The policymaking section is designed to evaluate the role of governmental policies and stakeholder engagement in facilitating FOWT projects. Questions in this section will explore the extent to which stakeholders are involved in the permitting process, the transparency and effectiveness of decision-making processes, and the impact of governmental policies on stakeholder perceptions. This section aims to gather data that will help identify best practices for enhancing policy frameworks and fostering positive stakeholder relationships.

Social Acceptance: Understanding the public perception, awareness, and acceptance of FOWT is crucial for the success of these projects. This section of the survey will address questions related to the general awareness of FOWT among different socio-economic sectors, the perceived benefits and drawbacks of FOWT, the level of trust in developers and authorities, and the effectiveness of communication and engagement strategies. The goal is to identify socio-economic barriers and enablers, propose strategies to improve public understanding and acceptance, and reduce social conflicts.

Environmental Impact: The environmental impact section will focus on gathering stakeholders' views on the ecological implications of FOWT deployment. This includes potential impacts on marine life, seabirds, and coastal ecosystems, as well as the perceived environmental benefits such as reduced greenhouse gas emissions and habitat creation. The

survey aims to balance development with ecological sustainability by understanding stakeholders' environmental concerns and benefits, informing strategies that integrate environmental considerations into project planning and implementation.

Financial and Market Analysis: This section is dedicated to understanding the financial aspects of FOWT investments. Questions will cover the perceived financial viability of FOWT projects, the availability of funding and subsidies, the risks associated with investing in emerging technologies, and key financial metrics such as Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), Return on Investment (ROI), and payback periods. The objective is to identify financial barriers and opportunities, propose strategies to attract investment, and foster market growth for FOWT.

Techno-Economic Analysis: The techno-economic analysis section evaluates the technological and economic feasibility of FOWT projects. This includes assessing technology readiness levels, cost efficiency, and potential market expansion opportunities. Questions will explore the perceived advantages and disadvantages of different FOWT technologies, the potential for cost reductions through technological advancements, and the scalability of FOWT solutions. Insights gained from this section will help in developing strategies to improve the competitiveness and feasibility of FOWT as a mainstream renewable energy source.

Each section of the survey is designed to capture detailed and actionable insights from various stakeholders, including policymakers, industry experts, environmentalists, and local communities. By gathering and analysing this data, the MARINEWIND project aims to develop comprehensive strategies to support the widespread adoption of FOWT, ultimately contributing to the global transition towards sustainable energy. The following sections provide a detailed breakdown of the survey methodology, the specific questions included, and the intended use of the collected data. By engaging with this document, stakeholders will gain a deeper understanding of the survey's objectives and how their contributions can help shape the future of floating offshore wind technology.

Methodology of the analysis

The data collected will be analysed to identify trends and common opinions among stakeholders. An assessment of the distribution of responses will be conducted, and any correlations between stakeholder opinion and various factors, such as nationality, professional roles, experience in the energy sector, and environmental awareness, will be identified. Additionally, comments and open-ended responses will provide qualitative insights into stakeholders' opinions and concerns.

3. POLICYMAKING

3.1 Policymaking QUESTIONNAIRE EXPLANATION AND OBJECTIVES

Once FOWT has reached its maturity, a well-defined policy framework is fundamental to support the development of commercial-scale wind farms in European countries and enable investors to operate in a safe and low-risk market. This section of the survey aims to better understand the current policy situation both in MARINEWIND countries and in other countries where FOWT is seen as a solution to meet the 2050 decarbonization goals, by delving into the preliminary results of the policy analysis in WP1 and the co-creation workshops conducted in the country labs. Specifically, these questions focus on stakeholders' perception of the policy framework for offshore wind in their countries, governments' commitment to and support for an offshore wind supply chain, data collection on barriers and enabling factors associated with the permitting process for FOWT, and types of fees, charges, and taxes related to offshore wind, also with the goal of understanding the direct impact and benefits on citizens and local communities.

Perception and awareness questions

Question 6 assesses the level of the government's commitment on (F)OWT perceived by the different stakeholders in their countries

Purpose: Question 6 aims to gauge respondents' perceptions of governmental commitment to floating offshore wind technology (FOWT) farms. Understanding the level of perceived commitment helps identify gaps between policy intentions and public perception, potentially highlighting areas needing more transparent communication or policy adjustment. Furthermore, this question also seeks to understand the strategic framework guiding offshore wind development in different countries. The approach—whether plan-led, developer-led, or hybrid—indicates the level of governmental versus private sector involvement and control in the development process.

Data Collection: The data collected here is qualitative, based on personal perceptions and experiences. By categorizing responses into low, medium, and high commitment levels, we can create a perception index. This index will help in comparing different countries or regions within a country, giving insights into where authorities are perceived as lagging or excelling in their support for FOWT development.

Question 7 the awareness of the stakeholders themselves in the consenting process.

Purpose: The purpose of this question is to assess the engagement and awareness levels of stakeholders during the critical permitting phase of FOWT projects. High stakeholder awareness and response are crucial for the smooth progression of these projects, as it ensures that all concerns and regulations are adequately addressed.

Data Collection: This question gathers qualitative data, which can be categorized into low, medium, and high levels of engagement. This categorization will help in creating a stakeholder engagement profile for different regions or projects.

Questions 8 still focus on the government's commitment to offshore wind, analysing any national initiatives to support the offshore wind supply chain and to monitor the cost of offshore wind.

Purpose: This question aims to determine the extent and nature of governmental support available to investors in the FOWT supply chain. Such support is critical for attracting investment and facilitating the development of the FOWT industry.

Data Collection: The data collected includes both binary (yes /no) responses and qualitative details about the types of support provided. This combination allows for a comprehensive understanding of governmental incentives and support mechanisms.

Usage: The information will be used to map the landscape of governmental support for FOWT investments. Identifying the types and levels of support available can highlight best practices and areas where additional support is needed. This data is valuable for investors considering entering the FOWT market, as it provides insights into the financial and regulatory incentives available. Policymakers can also use this data to enhance support structures, making them more attractive to investors and thus boosting the growth of the FOWT industry.

The aim of this first part is to possibly identify the countries where the government is highly committed to offshore wind: These countries could have an efficient policy framework from which to derive best practices and suggestions for other countries in the direction of a European-wide permitting process for FOWT.

Consenting process barriers and enablers questions

Questions 9 explores the topic of consenting process barriers, respectively.

Purpose: This question seeks to identify the primary obstacles encountered during the consenting process for offshore wind projects. Understanding these barriers is essential for streamlining processes and removing obstacles that hinder the development of FOWT projects.

Data Collection: The data collected is qualitative and multi-faceted, encompassing various potential barriers such as process complexity, legislative gaps, interstate disputes, and opposition from stakeholders. Respondents are asked to select from a list of common barriers or provide additional ones in a text box.

Usage: The collected data will be used to identify and prioritize the most significant barriers to FOWT deployment. This information is critical for policymakers and regulatory bodies

aiming to streamline the consenting process. By addressing these barriers, they can facilitate faster and more efficient project approvals. The insights gained can also inform advocacy efforts, guiding stakeholders in their engagement with authorities to push for necessary reforms and improvements in the regulatory framework.

Question 10 explores the topic of enabling factors.

Purpose: This question aims to identify the factors that facilitate the consenting process for FOWT projects. Understanding these enablers can help replicate successful strategies and practices across different regions and projects.

Data Collection: The data collected is qualitative, with respondents selecting from a list of enablers or providing additional suggestions in a text box. The enablers range from institutional bodies and task forces to investment in infrastructure and cultural awareness.

Usage: The data will be used to highlight best practices and successful strategies that have facilitated the consenting process in various contexts. Policymakers and industry stakeholders can use this information to implement or advocate for similar enablers in other regions. Identifying these key factors can lead to more efficient and streamlined consenting processes, reducing delays and increasing the likelihood of project success. Additionally, this data can support the development of policy recommendations and industry standards aimed at optimizing the consenting process for FOWT projects.

Question 11 highlights the topic of National Maritime Spatial Plans (required by Directive 2014/89/EU - Maritime Spatial Planning) in relation to the definition of designated areas for offshore wind farms to accelerate their development.

Purpose: The purpose of this question is to evaluate the perceived impact of defining specific areas for FOWT installation within maritime spatial planning. This planning is crucial for the organized and efficient deployment of offshore wind projects.

Data Collection: The data collected is qualitative, with respondents rating the significance of maritime spatial planning in three categories: not significant, marginally significant, and critically significant. This allows for a clear assessment of the perceived importance of spatial planning.

Usage: The data will be used to assess the importance of maritime spatial planning in the deployment of FOWT projects. High ratings of significance indicate a strong need for well-defined spatial planning to facilitate project implementation. Policymakers can use this information to prioritize the development of comprehensive maritime spatial plans that designate specific areas for FOWT installations. This can help in reducing conflicts with other marine activities, ensuring environmental protection, and expediting the deployment process.

By understanding the perceived importance, efforts can be focused on enhancing spatial planning frameworks to support the growth of the FOWT industry.

Question 12 addresses whether investors should apply for special permits to fund offshore wind farm projects.

Purpose: This question aims to determine whether there are special regulatory requirements for investors funding FOWT projects. Understanding these requirements is essential for identifying potential administrative hurdles in the investment process.

Data Collection: The data collected is binary (yes/no), providing a straightforward assessment of whether special permits are required for FOWT investments. This clarity helps in understanding the regulatory landscape for investors.

Usage: The data will be used to identify potential regulatory barriers that investors might face. If special permits are required, it may indicate additional administrative steps that could deter investment. Policymakers can use this information to streamline the permitting process, making it more investor-friendly. By reducing bureaucratic obstacles, it becomes easier to attract investment into the FOWT sector. This data is also valuable for potential investors, providing them with a clear understanding of the regulatory requirements and helping them prepare accordingly.

The objective of this second part is to collect data from different stakeholders on their perceptions of the most common barriers and enabling factors to FOWT development. This collection will add information to the list of barriers and enabling factors already collected in the national workshops through the national policy analyses and co-creation workshops conducted in WP1 in order to develop solutions to enable sustainable and informed FOWT.

Taxes and fees framework on FOWT

Question 13 explores the measurements used by the government to monitor the costs (CAPEX and OPEX) of the FOWT projects.

Purpose: This question aims to understand whether and how governments monitor the costs associated with offshore wind projects. Effective cost monitoring is crucial for ensuring the financial viability and transparency of these projects.

Data Collection: The data collected includes both binary (yes/no) responses and detailed qualitative information about the specific measures used for cost monitoring, such as cost-benefit analysis, tendering processes, and post-implementation reviews.

Usage: The information will be used to evaluate the extent and methods of governmental cost monitoring. Understanding the measures in place can highlight best practices and areas

needing improvement. Effective cost monitoring ensures that projects remain financially sustainable and that public funds are used efficiently. Policymakers can use this data to enhance cost monitoring frameworks, ensuring greater transparency and accountability. This data also helps investors and stakeholders understand the financial oversight mechanisms, building confidence in the financial management of offshore wind projects.

Questions 14, 15, and 16 explore possible rights on proceeds from local/national governments, as is the case with royalties in the O&G sector and look at the taxes, fees, and charges required for the construction of a (F)OWT farm and its operation, respectively.

Purpose: This question seeks to identify the financial rights and revenue mechanisms public authorities have regarding proceeds from FOWT farms. Understanding these financial relationships is crucial for evaluating the economic benefits and burdens of FOWT projects on different governmental levels.

Data Collection: The data collected includes binary (yes/no) responses regarding public authority rights on proceeds and detailed information about specific taxes, charges, and fees, as well as the administrative levels (national, regional, municipal) that collect these revenues.

Usage: The data will be used to map out the fiscal framework surrounding FOWT projects, highlighting how proceeds are distributed across different administrative levels. This information is valuable for assessing the economic impact of FOWT farms on local and national economies. Policymakers can use this data to develop fair and efficient revenue-sharing mechanisms that ensure all relevant authorities benefit from FOWT projects. The findings can also inform negotiations and agreements related to revenue distribution, ensuring that financial benefits are equitably shared and that potential fiscal challenges are addressed.

Question 17 and 18 investigate whether citizens and local communities where offshore wind farms are “located” have any kind of benefits from the presence of these facilities.

Purpose: These questions aim to determine whether governments provide benefits to local communities and consumers where offshore wind farms are installed. Understanding these benefits is important for assessing the social impact and acceptance of FOWT projects.

Data Collection: The data collected is binary (yes/no), providing a clear indication of whether such benefits exist. This simplicity allows for straightforward analysis of governmental policies towards local communities.

Usage: The information will be used to evaluate the extent of governmental support for communities hosting FOWT projects. If benefits such as reduced electricity costs are provided, it indicates a commitment to ensuring that local communities share in the economic and social benefits of these projects. Policymakers can use this data to design and implement community benefit schemes that enhance local support and acceptance of FOWT projects. This data is

also valuable for developers and investors, as community support is a critical factor in the successful implementation of offshore wind projects. By understanding and addressing local concerns and benefits, projects are more likely to achieve long-term sustainability and community integration.

This final part aims to understand what kind of taxes and fees are required of FOWT investors during the whole lifecycle of the wind farms. But it is of interest to the consortium to know whether public authorities have “royalties” on OWFs and the local communities where the offshore wind farms are developed have any kind of benefits (e.g. reduced electricity costs).

(These two survey topics are also analysed in more detail in the market analysis in section 6 and in social acceptance analysis in section 4).

4. SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

4.1 Social acceptance QUESTIONNAIRE EXPLANATION AND OBJECTIVES

Floating offshore wind technology (FOWT) will play a crucial role in the energy transition in several countries. However, a few prototypes and pre-commercial offshore wind farms in less than 10 countries worldwide can cause uncertainty of the population and the socioeconomic sectors (fisheries, tourism, and citizens) of those areas where FOWT can be deployed. The socio-economic questions section of the MARINEWIND survey aims to gather the perception of the potential socio-economic barriers and enablers, but also strategies to reduce the social conflicts around the deployment of FOWT across MARINEWIND countries (Spain, UK, Portugal, Greece and Italy) and the level of awareness, knowledge and acceptance on FOWT. By collecting data on various aspects related to socio-economic impact on different sectors such as fisheries, tourism, energy sector, social acceptance, we develop and identify solutions to conflict generation and a proper deployment of FOWT.

Perception and awareness questions

Understanding the perceived significance of FOWT as an opportunity for energy transition based on the knowledge about this technology is fundamental from a socioeconomic perspective. This analysis requires respondents to evaluate the importance of floating offshore wind farms within the renewable energy sector.

Level of awareness

A *high* level of awareness indicates that a significant portion of the population is well-informed about FOWT. People have a good understanding of how this technology works, its benefits and its impacts, both positive and negative, and its role in the renewable energy landscape.

A *medium* level of awareness suggests that the general population has some knowledge of FOWT, but it is not comprehensive. People might be aware of its existence and basic principles

but lack detailed understanding or insight into . This level of awareness indicates that while some information has reached the public, there is room for improvement in education and outreach efforts.

A *low* level of awareness signifies that most of the population is not familiar with FOWT. There is little to no recognition of its existence, how it functions, or its importance in the context of renewable energy. This suggests a significant gap in public knowledge and highlights the need for extensive education and awareness campaigns.

Lead consultancy

It is highly interesting to know if the government in different regions has involved different stakeholders in the consultancy process as it is considered one of the main strategies to solve conflicts around FOWT deployment. Being analysed jointly with other socioeconomic questions of this survey allows us to understand the impact of consultancy process application on the perception of FOWT.

A *yes* response indicates that the government or regional administration is actively involved in leading a public consultancy process or managing stakeholder engagement. This includes efforts such as organising public consultations, facilitating discussions among stakeholders, and running communication campaigns focused on offshore wind projects and climate change. This suggests a proactive approach by authorities to involve citizens and stakeholders in the decision-making process. It shows a commitment to transparency, public participation, and education. Such efforts are likely to increase public awareness, foster trust, and build support for offshore wind projects and broader climate change initiatives.

A *no* response signifies that the government or regional administration is not engaged in leading a public and open consultancy process or managing actively stakeholder engagement related to offshore wind projects and climate change awareness. This points to a lack of formal efforts by the authorities to involve the public or communicate effectively about offshore wind projects and their impact on climate change. It may indicate missed opportunities for fostering public understanding and support. Without such engagement, there could be gaps in public knowledge, potential resistance to projects, and a weaker overall response to climate change initiatives.

Under your knowledge questions (good solution for climate change, acceptance and knowledge)

The purpose of those three questions is to gather the perception around the and how the acceptance and the knowledge have changed thanks to initiatives such as MarineWind, allowing us to measure how our project impacts. It is expected to gather insights on how they are correlated from the answers of this survey.

Related to the perception of FOWT as a good solution to climate change and could be compatible with the environment and socioeconomic sectors in its surroundings, the answers imply:

Totally Agree: This response indicates a very strong positive sentiment. Respondents who choose "totally agree" believe wholeheartedly in the statement's validity. For these questions, it means they are highly convinced of FOWT's benefits for climate change, its compatibility with environmental and socioeconomic factors, their improved acceptance and understanding of FOWT, and their increased awareness of its policies and impacts.

Agree: This response indicates a positive but slightly less strong agreement with the statement. Respondents generally believe the statement is true but with some minor reservations or less intensity of belief compared to "totally agree." This reflects a positive perception, indicating that respondents see the value and potential of FOWT but might still have some areas of uncertainty or less pronounced enthusiasm.

Neither Agree nor Disagree: This neutral response suggests ambivalence or a lack of strong opinion on the statement. Respondents do not have enough information or conviction to lean one way or the other. This indicates a potential gap in knowledge or engagement. Respondents might need more information or clarity to form a stronger opinion.

Disagree: This response indicates a negative sentiment towards the statement. Respondents who choose "disagree" believe the statement is not accurate or true. This reflects scepticism or opposition, suggesting that respondents are not convinced of FOWT's benefits or their understanding and acceptance have not improved significantly.

Totally Disagree: This response indicates a very strong negative sentiment. Respondents who choose "totally disagree" are firmly against the statement and do not believe it to be true at all. This suggests significant scepticism or strong opposition.

Social barriers and enablers questions

Social barriers

Importance of different FOWT barriers, distinguishing between low, medium and high impact, and identifying those that are most relevant in the respondent's country of origin.

Low: This response indicates that the barrier is perceived to have minimal impact on concerns regarding the deployment of FOWT. Respondents believe that this factor is not a major issue. This suggests that the particular barrier is not seen as a significant hindrance to the deployment of FOWT in the respondent's view.

Medium: This response suggests that the barrier is seen as moderately impactful. It is a concern but not the most critical one. This indicates that while the barrier should be considered, it may not be the highest priority.

High: This response signifies that the barrier is viewed as very impactful and a major concern against the deployment of FOWT. This highlights the barrier as a top priority that needs significant attention and resources to address.

Relevant to Your Country: This response indicates that the specific barrier is particularly pertinent and impactful in the respondent's country. This suggests that the barrier is a local or national issue that significantly affects the deployment of FOWT within the country.

Social enablers

Importance of different FOWT enablers, distinguishing between low, medium and high impact, and identifying those that are most relevant in the respondent's country of origin.

Low: This response indicates that the enabler is perceived to have minimal impact on increasing the acceptance of FOWT. Respondents believe that this factor is not very influential.

Medium: This response suggests that the enabler is seen as moderately impactful. It contributes to acceptance but is not the most critical factor. This indicates that while the enabler should be considered, it may not be the highest priority.

High: This response signifies that the enabler is viewed as very impactful and a major driver for increasing the acceptance of FOWT. This highlights the enabler as a top priority that needs significant attention and resources to promote.

Relevant to Your Country: This response indicates that the specific enabler is particularly pertinent and impactful in the respondent's country. This suggests that the enabler is a local or national factor that significantly affects the acceptance of FOWT within the country.

Strategies and tools to analyse and minimise social conflict

Relevance of strategies to reduce social conflict in FOWTs, distinguishing between low, medium and high impact, and identifying those that are most relevant in the respondent's country of origin.

Low: This response indicates that the strategy is perceived to have minimal impact on reducing social conflicts around the deployment of FOWT. Respondents believe that this strategy is not very effective. This suggests that the particular strategy may not be worth prioritising or investing significant resources in.

Medium: This response suggests that the strategy is seen as moderately successful. It can help reduce social conflicts, but it is not the most effective method. This indicates that while the strategy should be considered, it may not be the highest priority.

High: This response signifies that the strategy is viewed as highly successful and very effective in reducing social conflicts around the deployment of FOWT. This highlights the strategy as a top priority that needs significant attention and resources.

Relevant to Your Country: This response indicates that the specific strategy is particularly pertinent and impactful in the respondent's country. This suggests that the strategy is a local or national solution that significantly affects the reduction of social conflicts within the country.

5. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

5.1 Environmental impact QUESTIONNAIRE EXPLANATION AND OBJECTIVES

Although the role of offshore wind generation in the global decarbonisation process is widely recognised, a careful assessment of the impact on marine ecosystems is crucial to accelerate the full exploitation of this new technology. In this context, it is important to consider the views of all stakeholders involved in the process from citizens to industrial developers. Furthermore, European sea basins have very different characteristics in terms of seabed, biodiversity, level of exploitation, response to climate change, so it is necessary to acquire information from a wider community than that represented by the MARINEWIND consortium. The survey aims to broaden the available information to support developers, policy makers and other stakeholders involved in the offshore wind energy sector, helping them to better understand environmental impacts, identify tools that can foster fair and transparent information, guide the permitting process and make informed decisions to minimise negative impacts and maximise environmental benefits for a fast and just implementation of FOWTs.

Perception and awareness questions

Reducing the reasons for opposition from stakeholders including citizens, is crucial to speeding up the authorisation process. The questions of the MARINEWIND survey included in this section aim to understand stakeholders' perceptions regarding the environmental impacts of floating offshore wind turbines, collecting opinions and evaluations compared to other energy sources. Additionally, it seeks to understand the importance of active involvement of the local community in FOWT projects, evaluating stakeholders' awareness levels regarding the environmental impacts and benefits of such installations, and determining the importance of educational programs and information on offshore wind energy.

Environmental barriers and enablers questions

On the basis of technical and scientific literature, information gathered during national labs and the specific experience of MARINEWIND's partners in the offshore wind sector, the possible impacts on the marine environment of FOWTs during the installation, operational and decommissioning phases were identified and classified in terms of intensity. However, there is still no general consensus among the various stakeholders regarding the severity of certain stressors in the short and long term. Most of the available analyses are largely based on the data available for bottom-fixed wind turbines in the Baltic and North Seas that cannot be directly applied to predict the effects of floating turbines anchored on the deep seafloor.

Moreover, the effects of FOWTs are highly dependent on the specificity of the basins. Finally, it is important to assess not only the environmental impact of the individual farm but the cumulative impact produced by the installation of all those planned for the coming years.

Conversely, the installation of FOWTs produces a number of direct and indirect environmental benefits that need to be emphasised.

The questions in this section are therefore aimed at gathering the views, particularly of stakeholders with expertise in environmental issues (marine biologists and geologists, oceanographers) to consolidate the results of the analysis carried out on the environmental impacts and benefits of FOWTs and their specific relevance. These results represent the input for the development of robust criteria for the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) of these installations and for Cumulative Impact Assessment methodologies that can help authorities at correctly managing the marine environment.

Strategies and tools to analyse and minimise the environmental impact questions

The studies performed so far clearly highlighted that the evaluation of environmental impact analyses is one of the main reasons for slow authorisation processes in all countries. This is due to various factors including the lack of:

- I. a clear regulations
- II. complete knowledge on the characteristics of marine areas,
- III. robust tools of analysis
- IV. specialised skills.

The environmental impact section of the MARINEWIND survey, includes questions designed to identify the key needs and gaps that must be addressed to conduct accurate environmental impact analyses and, if necessary, develop mitigation strategies or remediation measures.

Other critical issues that emerged from the analysis concern procedural differences not only between different countries sharing contiguous marine areas but also at regional level within the same country. To overcome these challenges causing conflicts and delays in authorization processes, it is therefore crucial to understand from all stakeholders involved in the environmental analysis whether it is necessary to establish unambiguous criteria and procedures at sea- basin, European or global level.

6. FINANCIAL AND MARKET ANALYSIS

6.1 Financial analysis QUESTIONNAIRE EXPLANATION AND OBJECTIVES

The floating offshore wind market represents a growing sector within the renewable energy industry, offering significant opportunities and challenges to the stakeholders. A comprehensive financial and statistical analysis requires meticulous data collection through well-structured survey questions. These questions focus on various financial metrics and

perceptions crucial for understanding the market dynamics, risks, and returns associated with floating offshore wind technology (FOWT). This deliverable provides an in-depth analysis of the survey questions designed to gather financial data about the FOWT market in the MARINEWIND labs, with a particular focus on financial barriers and enablers to investments in the FOWT sector, Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), Return on Investment (ROI), Net Present Value (NPV), risk adjusted extra returns (Risk Premium), and Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR).

Perception and Awareness Questions

Significance of Floating Offshore Wind Farms as an Investment Opportunity

Understanding the perceived significance of FOWT as an investment opportunity is fundamental. This question asks respondents to rate the significance of floating offshore wind farms within the renewable energy industry. The response options range from highly significant, moderately significant, to insignificant. A rating of "highly significant" indicates strong investor interest and recognition of FOWT's potential for substantial returns and strategic importance in renewable energy portfolios. Conversely, a "moderately significant" rating suggests a cautious but positive outlook, where investors see potential but may have reservations due to factors such as technological maturity or regulatory uncertainty. An "insignificant" rating reflects a lack of confidence or awareness, pointing to potential areas for improving market education and outreach. Understanding these perceptions helps gauge investor sentiment and the perceived value of FOWT relative to other renewable energy sources.

- **Financial and Statistical Analysis Methodology:** The responses can be statistically analyzed using descriptive statistics to determine the distribution of perceptions. Cross-tabulation can be applied to understand how different respondent demographics (e.g., industry experience, geographic location) influence perceptions. Further, sentiment analysis can be performed to interpret open-ended responses, providing deeper insights into investor attitudes.

Perceived Level of Risk

Assessing the perceived risk associated with FOWT investments compared to traditional investments is critical for understanding investor behaviour and decision-making. This question asks respondents to rate the level of risk they associate with investing in FOWT. A perception of "high risk" may indicate concerns about the nascent technology, high capital costs, and regulatory challenges. On the other hand, a "medium risk" rating suggests a balanced view where risks are acknowledged but considered manageable, possibly due to emerging technological advancements or supportive policies. A "low risk" perception implies that FOWT is seen as a mature, stable investment, comparable to other well-established

renewable energy sources. These risk perceptions influence investment decisions and highlight areas where additional risk mitigation strategies may be necessary.

- **Financial and Statistical Analysis Methodology:** Risk perception data can be analysed using risk assessment frameworks. Quantitative risk analysis techniques, such as Monte Carlo simulations, can model potential financial outcomes based on perceived risk levels. Sensitivity analysis can identify which factors most influence risk perceptions, helping prioritise risk management strategies.

Expected Financial Returns

This question evaluates the anticipated financial returns from FOWT investments compared to other options, providing insights into investor expectations and potential market attractiveness. Respondents are asked to rate their expectations of financial returns as higher, comparable, or lower than other investments. Expectations of "higher financial returns" indicate that investors see FOWT as a promising investment with superior returns, possibly due to innovative technology, high energy yield, or supportive policies. "Comparable financial returns" suggest that investors view FOWT as a viable alternative, offering returns on par with other investments. However, expectations of "lower financial returns" may highlight concerns about high initial costs, operational challenges, or market volatility. Understanding these expectations helps identify the factors driving investor interest and areas needing improvement to enhance market appeal.

- **Financial and Statistical Analysis Methodology:** ROI, NPV, and IRR calculations can be performed on anticipated financial return data to quantify expected profitability. Comparative analysis with other investment sectors can highlight FOWT's relative attractiveness. Regression analysis can explore relationships between expected returns and perceived risks or other influencing factors.

Redistribution of Funds from FOWT

Understanding the priorities for redistributing funds generated by FOWT projects within local communities can provide insights into social and economic impacts. This section asks respondents to select the top priorities for redistributing funds generated by FOWT. Options include renewable energy infrastructure, job creation and training programs, affordable housing initiatives, environmental conservation and restoration, community education and awareness, support for SMEs, climate change adaptation and resilience, technological innovation, and waste management and recycling programs. Additionally, there is an option for respondents to specify other priorities. These responses help identify the community benefits that stakeholders prioritise, informing strategies to ensure that FOWT projects contribute to local development and sustainability.

- **Financial and Statistical Analysis Methodology:** The data on fund redistribution priorities can be analysed using frequency analysis to determine the most common priorities. Weighted scoring models can evaluate the importance of each priority relative to others. Impact assessment methodologies can be used to predict the social and economic outcomes of various fund redistribution strategies.

Financial Barriers

Identifying financial barriers to investing in FOWT is crucial for developing strategies to mitigate these challenges. This section asks respondents to select the barriers they have encountered in their experience with offshore floating wind projects. Options include lack of funding, lack of government support, lack of communication between developers, marine planners, and coastal communities, high LCOE, high manufacturing costs, high operating and maintenance costs, underdeveloped supply chain, limited port and installation infrastructure, long installation and decommissioning times, negative stakeholder impact on project timelines, lack of standardisation, fluctuating energy prices, and high taxes or fees. By identifying these barriers, stakeholders can develop targeted strategies to address the most pressing challenges, enhancing the feasibility and attractiveness of FOWT investments.

- **Financial and Statistical Analysis Methodology:** Barrier data can be analyzed using factor analysis to identify underlying patterns and key barrier categories. SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) analysis can provide a strategic framework for addressing these barriers. Survey responses can be analysed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns.

Financial Enablers

Understanding the financial incentives and support mechanisms that encourage investment in FOWT is essential for promoting market growth. This section asks respondents to select the financial incentives or support mechanisms that are relevant in their country. Options include grants and subsidies, low-interest loans, green bonds and climate funds, infrastructure support and co-financing, feed-in tariffs (FiTs), power purchase agreements (PPAs), innovation and R&D funding, investment tax credits (ITCs), production tax credits (PTCs), renewable energy certificates (RECs) and guarantees of origin (GOs). Additionally, there is an option for respondents to specify other mechanisms. These responses help identify the most effective financial enablers that can drive investment in FOWT projects, providing insights into policy and financial tools that can be leveraged to support market development.

- **Financial and Statistical Analysis Methodology:** The effectiveness of financial enablers can be evaluated using econometric modelling to assess their impact on investment levels. Scenario analysis can predict how different combinations of enablers might

influence market growth. Policy analysis frameworks can identify the most impactful regulatory and financial support mechanisms.

Additional Enablers:

This section asks respondents to select additional enablers that can support FOWT investments. Options include financial support to reduce investor risk, collaboration between government and financial institutions, policy support mechanisms to lower LCOE, platforms for knowledge sharing, improved communication between developers and stakeholders, government financing reforms to support OEMs, increased confidence in OEMs through warranties, and government interventions to reduce operating and manufacturing costs. These enablers highlight the importance of a supportive ecosystem, including financial, policy, and collaborative efforts, to foster a conducive environment for FOWT investments.

- **Financial and Statistical Analysis Methodology:** Survey responses can be analysed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns. Decision analysis tools can prioritise enablers based on their expected impact on investment attractiveness and market development. Implementation feasibility studies can assess the practical aspects of deploying these enablers.

Financial Solutions and Instruments

Identifying financial instruments available for FOWT projects is key for understanding the financing landscape. This section asks respondents to select the financial instruments offered by financial institutions for developing FOWT projects in their country. Options include construction loans, term loans, bridge loans, revolving credit lines, export credit financing, green bonds, loan guarantees, interest rate swaps, collateralized debt obligations (CDOs), subordinated debts, soft loans, and mezzanine financing. Additionally, there is an option for respondents to specify other instruments. These responses provide insights into the diversity and availability of financial products that can support FOWT projects, helping stakeholders understand the financing options and their implications for project development and risk management.

- **Financial and Statistical Analysis Methodology:** Financial instrument data can be analysed using financial engineering techniques to model their impact on project financing. Risk-return profiles can be developed for each instrument to evaluate their suitability for different project stages. Portfolio optimization methods can suggest the best mix of financial instruments to minimise costs and risks.

Investment Cost and Revenues

Collecting data on investment costs and revenues provides insights into the financial performance and viability of FOWT projects. This section asks respondents to provide information on various financial metrics, including annual growth trends, cumulative investments, total revenues, fixed maintenance and operating costs, variable maintenance and operating costs, and the debt-to-equity ratio in the FOWT sector. Respondents are asked whether they are aware of this information and, if so, to provide estimates. Understanding these metrics helps stakeholders assess the financial health and sustainability of FOWT projects, identifying areas for cost optimization and revenue enhancement.

- **Financial and Statistical Analysis Methodology:** Cost and revenue data can be analysed using financial ratio analysis to assess profitability, liquidity, and solvency. econometric analysis can track trends and forecast future financial performance. Comparative analysis with benchmarks from other renewable energy sectors can highlight strengths and weaknesses in financial performance.

Linking to Financial and Statistical Analysis Methodology

The data collected from the survey provides a comprehensive basis for financial and statistical analysis, focusing on key metrics like LCOE, ROI, NPV, risk premium, IRR, and CVaR. Here's how these analyses can be conducted using the survey data:

Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE):

- **Data Required:** Expected returns, cost data, discount rate, and energy production per FOWT.
- **Analysis:** Calculate LCOE by summing the total lifetime costs and dividing by the total energy output. Sensitivity analysis can explore how different financial enablers and barriers impact LCOE.

Return on Investment (ROI):

- **Data Required:** Expected financial returns, cost and revenue data.
- **Analysis:** ROI is calculated by dividing the net profit by the total investment cost. Comparative analysis can be done to see how ROI for FOWT compares to other renewable energy investments.

Net Present Value (NPV):

- **Data Required:** Expected returns, cost data, discount rate.
- **Analysis:** NPV is calculated by discounting future cash flows to their present value and subtracting the initial investment. Scenario analysis

can be used to see how changes in risk factors and financial enablers affect NPV.

Risk Premium:

- **Data Required:** expected returns.
- **Analysis:** The risk premium can be assessed by comparing the expected return of FOWT investments to the risk-free rate. Regression analysis can determine the factors contributing to the risk premium.

Internal Rate of Return (IRR):

- **Data Required:** Cost and revenue data.
- **Analysis:** IRR is the discount rate that makes the NPV of all cash flows from a particular project equal to zero. IRR can be compared across different investment scenarios to determine the most attractive projects.

Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR):

- **Data Required:** Risk perception data, financial performance data.
- **Analysis:** CVaR measures the expected loss in extreme scenarios. Monte Carlo simulations can model the distribution of financial outcomes and calculate CVaR to assess potential financial risks under adverse conditions.

To conclude, the financial survey questions are designed to capture a comprehensive range of financial data and investor perceptions, which are crucial for a detailed financial and statistical analysis of the floating offshore wind market. By analysing this data through various financial metrics and statistical methods, stakeholders can gain valuable insights into the market's dynamics, risks, and potential returns. This analysis will not only inform investment decisions but also help in developing strategies to overcome barriers, leverage enablers, and enhance the overall viability and attractiveness of FOWT projects.

6.2 Market analysis QUESTIONNAIRE EXPLANATION AND OBJECTIVES

The market section of the MARINEWIND survey aims to gather information about the barriers and enablers to Floating Offshore Wind Technologies (FOWT) commercialization across the MARINEWIND countries (Spain, UK, Portugal, Greece, Italy, and Belgium). The questions were developed to provide information supporting the design of different strategies for the commercialization of FOWT in these relevant geographies. By collecting data on various aspects related to the market, such as the engagement of strategic sectors, market

attractiveness, and its current global position, it is possible to define adapted solutions to strengthen the market in each analysed country. The market section of the survey contains 7 questions that address the following aspects:

1. The level of engagement of key stakeholders for the FOWT market (1 question).

This question facilitates the identification of key stakeholders driving market growth and highlights which stakeholder groups require strengthened engagement to advance the full commercialization of FOWT in the analysed country.

2. The level of market attractiveness for the implementation of FOWT (1 question).

By assessing key factors such as market size, stability, regional competitive environment, bankability of renewable energy, strength of the local supply chain, long-term energy strategy, market incentives, policy support mechanisms, as well as strategic aspects like cultural approach to FOWT and geographic location in relation to other potential FOWT markets, tailored strategies can be later developed to maintain or enhance market attractiveness in each country.

3. Exploring whether the country would initially rely on a domestic or international supply chain for large-scale deployment scenarios (1 question).
4. Identification and classification of market barriers, enablers, and opportunities (3 questions).

These questions aim to classify and identify the importance of various barriers, enablers, and opportunities for the commercialization of FOWT in each analysed country.

The answerer will rate factors regarding barriers, such as, public concerns or lack of awareness regarding the safety and aesthetics of offshore wind installations, unfavourable regulatory environment and the lack of long-term political frameworks, insufficient port facilities and infrastructure for manufacturing, assembly, and maintenance, high levels of marine traffic, including shipping lanes and fishing activities, lack of availability of specialised vessels and equipment, environmental impact and ecosystem concerns, issues with social acceptance and support from local communities, grid connection challenges, competition with established fixed-bottom offshore wind projects, complex permitting and approval processes, and, finally, lack of guaranteed market access or secure power purchase agreements.

Regarding different enablers, the survey will give us information on the importance of clear and consistent policies that provide incentives, subsidies, and a regulatory framework supporting the development of floating offshore wind projects, stable and predictable policy environment with long-term commitments, financial

incentives and subsidies, investments in R&D, investments in education and training programs to support the development of a skilled workforce, adequate investment in onshore and offshore grid infrastructure, collaboration between government entities and private industry, proactive and transparent engagement with local communities and stakeholders, cooperation with other countries, industry stakeholders, and international organisations, policies to promote a competitive market environment and the diversification of energy sources, development of infrastructure to support manufacturing and supply chain.

Finally, regarding opportunities for a market expansion on FOWT, the answerer will rate the importance of relevant factors such as relevant previous activity (reduces risk and facilitates market penetration), public support (through both technology-push and market-pull mechanisms), energy resource (significant over a relevant area), infrastructure capabilities (research infrastructures, dedicated facilities and test sites, ports for fabrication, assembly, quick reaction ports, electricity grid infrastructure), specific national research focus on the field, national targets concerning the share of offshore wind energy in gross final energy consumption, public processes such as marine spatial planning in place to facilitate efficient consenting, advantageous upcoming electricity market reforms, “One-stop-shop” platforms, partnerships between academia, the public and the private sector to foster innovation.

5. Open question exploring the essential policy support needed to facilitate the development of FOWT, as well as the potential implementation of tailored standards, certifications, and policy reforms to promote growth in the floating offshore wind market (1 question).

This question aims to explore the role of policy support, tailored standards, certifications, and reform policies in advancing the development of a more mature FOWT market in each analysed country.

7. TECHNO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

7.1 Techno-economic analysis QUESTIONNAIRE EXPLANATION AND OBJECTIVES

The techno-economic section of the MARINEWIND survey aims to address the current technological barriers of offshore wind and those arising from the novel frontier of floating offshore wind technology (FOWT). It will consider the correlation between these barriers and regional geographical characteristics, the impact on marine ecosystems, integration within the circular economy, and climate change. The goal is to propose ad-hoc technological solutions tailored to specific marine areas across MARINEWIND countries (Spain, UK, Portugal, Greece, Italy, and Belgium).

In addition, the survey examines the combination of different offshore technologies coupled with FOWTs, such as wave, tidal, floating PV devices, or hydrogen production. The analysis will assess the pros and cons, main challenges, and replicability issues of these hybrid technologies in various geographical areas to help understand the potential makeup of net-zero future systems related to integration, intermittency, asynchronous generation, and geographical locations of supply and demand to identify present challenges and future market opportunities.

KEY TECHNOLOGICAL BARRIERS:

Realising floating offshore wind's full potential requires overcoming several technological barriers and fostering an enabling environment through strategic investments, innovation, and collaboration. The questionnaire assesses the key technological barriers to accelerating FOWTs, particularly focussing on the following:

Stability and structural integrity of floating turbines: The survey seeks to understand the significant challenge of addressing the stability and structural integrity of floating turbines in harsh offshore environments, including strong winds, waves, and currents.

Anchoring and mooring systems: Developing robust anchoring and mooring systems that can withstand extreme marine conditions and maintain the position of floating turbines is crucial. The questions gather information supporting the design of different strategies for addressing anchoring and monitoring issues.

Transmission of electricity from offshore turbines to shore: Transmitting electricity over long distances from offshore wind farms to onshore grids poses technical challenges, particularly regarding cable design and efficiency.

Maintenance and accessibility: Maintaining and accessing turbines in remote offshore locations for repairs and maintenance can be logistically challenging and costly.

Maturity of design tools: The lack of mature integrated design tools specifically tailored for offshore wind turbines, particularly floating platforms, hinders optimal design and performance.

High-voltage dynamic cables: Developing high-voltage dynamic cables capable of withstanding the harsh offshore environment and accommodating the movement of floating turbines is a critical challenge.

Floating substations: Designing and constructing floating substations to collect and transmit electricity from offshore wind farms presents technical complexities.

Environmental impacts: Understanding and mitigating the coupled environmental impacts of offshore wind farms, such as on marine ecosystems and wildlife, is essential for sustainable development.

KEY TECHNOLOGICAL ENABLERS:

The development of high-voltage dynamic cables, cable connectors (e.g., wet-mate connectors), and floating substations are significant technological barriers currently limiting offshore wind energy deployment. Additionally, an improved understanding of coupled environmental impacts is needed. For floating offshore wind technology (FOWT) specifically, the high costs and immature technology pose challenges. Developing robust floating platforms that can withstand harsh marine conditions, optimising turbine design and placement for stability and maximising energy production, and the lack of standardisation in floating foundation concepts (limiting cost reductions) are key barriers. Limited options, scarce vessels for the installation of larger turbines, and constraints on the supply chain for mooring, dynamic cables, and towing floating structures are also significant hurdles.

Engineering and technological innovation are crucial to addressing the challenges related to floating platforms and turbine design. Achieving economies of scale as the technology matures can help reduce costs. Developing efficient logistics and port infrastructure for manufacturing, assembly, and maintenance is essential. Standardising floating foundation technologies can enable the adaptation of the supply chain. Government support, such as the UK's FLOWMIS scheme, can fund critical port infrastructure development. The search results highlight the need for innovation, standardisation, and infrastructure development to overcome the technological hurdles around cabling, substations, floating platforms, installation, and supply chain constraints, enabling offshore wind, especially floating offshore wind, to be deployed at scale.

Overcoming the technological barriers and leveraging the enablers through strategic investments, innovation, and collaboration will be crucial in unlocking the full potential of floating offshore wind and accelerating the global energy transition towards a sustainable future. This section of the questionnaire assesses the key technological enablers to accelerating FOWTs:

Logistics and port infrastructure: Establishing suitable port facilities for manufacturing, assembly, and maintenance, as well as efficient logistics for transporting turbines and components, is crucial for enabling the growth of the floating offshore wind sector.

Grid reinforcement: Strengthening and upgrading existing grid infrastructure to accommodate the integration of offshore wind energy is a necessary enabler.

Promoting standardisation and modularity in component design can streamline manufacturing processes, reduce costs, and optimise the supply chain.

Installation and operations optimisation: Developing innovative techniques and technologies for optimising floating offshore wind turbines' installation, operation, and maintenance can improve efficiency and reduce costs.

Research and development investments to address key challenges, such as component and substructure design, manufacturing techniques, and operational methods, are crucial for driving the sector's growth.

Establishing supportive government policies, regulations, and incentives to create an enabling environment that attracts investment and fosters industry growth.

International collaboration and partnerships: Fostering collaboration and partnerships among key international players, including data sharing and knowledge exchange, can accelerate technological advancements and drive innovation.

Hybrid offshore technologies: Integrating floating offshore wind with other renewable technologies, such as wave, tidal, and floating solar photovoltaics (PV), can create synergies and optimise energy production.

8. CONCLUSIONS

Through comprehensive data collection and analysis, the survey will address key challenges and opportunities associated with FOWT deployment providing valuable insights into several areas such as:

Policymaking: The survey will evaluate the level of governmental involvement in stakeholder engagement processes. It will gather data on the transparency of communication between stakeholders and authorities. This section aims to identify best practices for involving stakeholders in the decision-making process, thereby fostering public support and enhancing the effectiveness of policies that promote FOWT deployment. The data collected will be instrumental in understanding how different policy approaches impact stakeholder perceptions and the overall success of FOWT projects.

Social Acceptance: The survey will assess the awareness and acceptance of FOWT among different socio-economic sectors. It seeks to understand public perceptions of the benefits and drawbacks of FOWT, the level of trust in developers and authorities, and the effectiveness of current communication strategies. By identifying socio-economic barriers and enablers, the survey aims to propose strategies to enhance public understanding and acceptance of FOWT projects. This will help to reduce social conflicts and build a supportive community environment, which is essential for the successful implementation of FOWT technology.

Environmental Impact: The survey will gather stakeholders' views on the environmental implications of FOWT projects. This includes potential impacts on marine life, seabirds, and coastal ecosystems, as well as perceived environmental benefits such as reduced greenhouse gas emissions and the creation of new marine habitats. The survey aims to balance development with ecological sustainability by understanding concerns and benefits from an environmental perspective. The insights gained will inform strategies to minimise negative environmental impacts and enhance the positive contributions of FOWT to environmental sustainability.

Financial and Market Analysis: The survey will address financial perceptions, barriers, and opportunities related to FOWT investments. It will include an analysis of financial metrics like Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), Return on Investment (ROI), and payback periods. This section seeks to understand the financial viability of FOWT projects from the perspective of different stakeholders, including investors, developers, and policymakers. The data collected will help identify financial barriers and opportunities, inform strategies to attract investment, and foster market growth for FOWT. This analysis is crucial for ensuring that FOWT projects are financially sustainable and attractive to investors.

Technical Analysis: The survey will evaluate the technical and economic feasibility of FOWT projects. It aims to assess factors such as technology readiness levels, cost efficiency, and potential market expansion opportunities. Questions will cover the perceived advantages and disadvantages of different FOWT technologies, the potential for cost reductions through technological advancements, and the scalability of FOWT solutions. The insights gained will help in developing strategies to improve the competitiveness and feasibility of FOWT as a renewable energy source. This will ensure that FOWT technology can be deployed at scale and integrated into the broader energy market.

The comprehensive data collected from the MARINEWIND survey will provide a robust foundation for understanding the multi-faceted aspects of FOWT deployment. The analysis of this data will reveal trends, common opinions, and correlations between stakeholders' views and various factors such as nationality, professional roles, and environmental awareness. These insights will be invaluable for developing targeted strategies that address the specific needs and concerns of different stakeholder groups. Moreover, the survey will help identify potential conflicts and areas of convergence among stakeholders, facilitating the development of collaborative approaches to problem-solving. By understanding the diverse perspectives and interests of stakeholders, the MARINEWIND project can create more inclusive and effective strategies for FOWT deployment. The data collected will inform policies, enhance public acceptance, address environmental concerns, attract financial investment, and improve technological feasibility.

Annex: MARINEWIND Country specific financial barriers and enablers

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General Information

Demographic information:

1. What's the name of your organisation (optional)
2. What is your primary role or occupation:
 - Communities and their representatives
 - Consumers and consumer groups
 - Government representative (Public authority)
 - Engineering/ Energy Consultancy
 - Technology/ Project developers
 - Renewable Energy Company
 - SME/Innovator
 - Sites, Planning or Consenting
 - Networks
 - Political
 - Investor/Funding institution
 - Regulators
 - Financial analyst
 - Environmental organisation
 - Fisheries
 - Marine biologist
 - Academia/ Research
 - Other (Please specify)

3. Which country is your organisation from?

4. On a scale of 1-10, how would you rate your expertise in floating offshore wind technologies (FOWTs)?

5. Are you currently participating in or working on any offshore wind farm projects?
 - Yes
 - No

Section 1: Permits, governmental reforms, taxes and charges (policymaking)**6. Perception and /or awareness questions**

- In your perception, How committed are the relevant authorities in your country to supporting the development of FOWT farms to meet the EU's 2030/2050 energy targets?
 - low
 - medium
 - high

Please describe the overall approach to offshore wind development in your country:

- Plan-led
- Developer-led
- Hybrid

7. In your experience, what is the level of response/awareness from relevant stakeholders during the permitting process

- low
- Medium
- High

8. Does the government offer any support to potential investors in the FOWT supply chain?

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide details

9. What are the most significant barriers regarding the consenting process for offshore wind technology deployment in your country?

- Complexity and length of the process
- Lack of a specific Maritime Spatial Planning
- Lack or incompleteness of a specific legislation
- Interstate dispute with neighbouring countries
- Presence of marine protected areas
- Lack of adequate information to citizens and stakeholders on FOWT benefits/costs and impacts
- Opposition from some categories of stakeholders (e.g. fishermen)
- Electrical grid capacity
- Availability of funding or public investments in infrastructures
- Insufficient resources within the involved regulatory bodies
- Shortage of human resources available to handle future FOW projects
- Lack of a centralised institution managing the applications

10. What are the most significant enablers to the consenting process for offshore wind technology deployment in your country?

- Establishment of devoted coordination institutional bodies for the development of FOWTs
- Identification of specific maritime areas for the deployment of FOWTs
- EU recommendations to accelerate the consenting process
- Establishment of a multidisciplinary task force of experts to support ministries in the process
- Establishment of a “Stop shop” procedure
- Availability of a Maritime Spatial Planning identifying suitable FOWTs installation areas considering conflicts with other sectors
- Increase investments in storage systems and grid infrastructure
- Increase cultural awareness among citizens
- Establishment of a suitable auction system
- Creation of an extended network of companies with experience and capabilities for offshore wind activities (strong national supply chain)
- Presence of a strong shipyard or Oil & Gas industry
- Political interest in delivering an agile consenting process

11. In your opinion, how significant would the definition of specific area for FOWT installation in the Maritime Spatial Planning be to speed up the deployment?

- Not significant
- Marginally significant
- Critically significant

12. Do investors need to ask for special permits to fund FOWT?

- Yes
- No

13. Does the government monitor the cost of offshore wind projects?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what measures are used by the government to monitor the cost of offshore wind projects?

- Cost benefit analysis
- Tendering and auction processes
- Cost reporting requirements
- Risk mitigation measures
- Post implementation reviews
- Market monitoring and competition policy

- Other (please specify)

14. Does the public authority have any rights on the proceeds from FOWT farms?

- Yes
- No

15. Please select taxes, charges, or fees relevant to implementing a FOWT farm and which administration level collects these taxes.

- Corporate income tax
 - National level
 - Regional level
 - Municipal/local level
 - Specialised agencies
- Value-added Tax (VAT)
 - National level
 - Regional level
 - Municipal/local level
 - Specialised agencies
- Customs duties and import tax
 - National level
 - Regional level
 - Municipal/local level
 - Specialised agencies
- Licence and permit fees
 - National level
 - Regional level
 - Municipal/local level
 - Specialised agencies
- Environmental impact assessment (EIA) fees
 - National level
 - Regional level
 - Municipal/local level
 - Specialised agencies
- Employment taxes
 - National level
 - Regional level
 - Municipal/local level
 - Specialised agencies
- Renewable Energy Certificates (REC) fees
 - National level

- Regional level
- Municipal/local level
- Specialised agencies
- Social security contributions (*e.g. National insurance contribution in the UK*)
 - National level
 - Regional level
 - Municipal/local level
 - Specialised agencies

16. Which taxes, charges or fees apply during the operation of a FOWT farm?

- Corporate income tax
- Property tax
- Environmental impact assessment (EIA) fees
- Employment taxes
- Licence and permit renewal fees
- Insurance premiums
- Renewable Energy Certificate (REC) compliance cost
- Social security contributions, *e.g. (National insurance contribution in the UK)*

17. Does the government offer any kind of benefits for local communities and consumers where offshore wind farms are installed? (e.g. reduced electricity costs for the consumer)?

- Yes
- No

Section 2: Social acceptance

Perception and awareness questions

18. In your perception, how significant are the following barriers to increasing concerns against deploying floating offshore wind technology? Which are more relevant to your country?

				Relevant to your country
	Low	Medium	High	
Impact of FOWT on the loss of fishing grounds.				
Impact of FOWT on the fishermen's flexibility and restriction on their operability				
Impact on traveling time for fisheries, local communities, and goods and services marine transportation routes (due to having to go around the farm)				

Impact on fishermen regarding the security of employment, income, and decision making.				
Impact of FOWT safety rules, co-location, and displacement on unhealthy fisheries competitiveness.				
Impact of FOWT on the fishing market in coastal communities.				
Impact of reduced fishing grounds due to FOWT on the unhealthy competition among local fishermen.				
Impact of FOWT on fishermen’s fishing gear.				
Impact of FOWT noise on coastal resorts and hotels in the area during construction, maintenance, and operation periods.				
Impact of FOWT on Aquaculture.				
Real estate value reduction.				
Recreational boating and sports activities limited or affected by the FOWT farm.				
Agriculture income reduction.				
Cultural heritage.				

19. Under your perception, how significant are the following **enablers** to increase the acceptance of floating offshore wind technology?

				Relevant to your country
	Low	Medium	High	
Positive gross added value				
New activities related to tourism/recreational boating.				
New activities related to R&D on				

marine energy development or monitoring of environmental aspects.				
Employment generation				
Development of the supply chain of the FOWT.				
Specialised training and education related to FOWT.				
Compatibility of uses (including aquaculture, tourism, fisheries activities).				
Artificial reef and marine protected areas.				
Development of communication platforms.				
Lower electricity rate				

20. Under your perception, how successful would the following strategies be in reducing the social conflicts around the deployment of floating offshore wind technology? Which are more relevant to your country?

				Relevant to your country
	Low	Medium	High	
Including socioeconomic criteria to award projects as a strategy to increase project integration (from a socioeconomic and environmental point of view) in its surroundings				
Criteria on FOWT farm design that reduce its impact (buried onshore evacuation line, buried offshore evacuation line, distance from shore, etc.)				
Apprenticeship and Scholarship programmes: training programs, financial contributions to education,				

or educational programs for local schools to learn about climate change, sustainability and renewable energy.				
Direct investment and project Funds to support local communities in the surrounding areas to the FOWT farm (Contribution to charitable causes, supporting energy transition and local business, supporting women empowerment programmes, infrastructure improvements, support local tourism activities)				
Electricity discounts in the surrounding areas to the FOWT farm and increase in internet speed.				
Engagement of local communities in the equity of the FOWT farm (community ownership) through solutions such as crowdfunding, raising capital from local SME entrepreneurs, etc.				
Affected sectors, such as fishermen, provide services during the development, execution, and O&M stages, as well as the touristic sector, with visitor centres, boat trips, information boards, etc.				
Community engagement activities. A website explaining the projects, meetings, and events explaining the project				
Informing and involving the local community from the outset of a floating wind turbine project, making them aware of both the advantages and disadvantages				

21.What is the level of awareness of FOWT among the country's general population?

- High
- Medium
- Low

22.Does the government or any local/regional administration lead a public consultancy process or something similar

to managing stakeholders' engagement (e.g., the concentration process on offshore wind projects in France) or a communication campaign around offshore wind and climate change to increase citizen awareness?

- Yes
- No

23. Do you believe that FOWTs are a good solution for combating climate change and that they can be compatible with the surrounding environment and socioeconomic sectors?

- Totally agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Totally disagree

24. Considering the socioeconomic, environmental potential impacts and policies related to FOWT, has your acceptance, awareness, and knowledge of FOWT improved?

- Totally agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Totally disagree

25. Is public and stakeholder support, including community engagement, critical for the success of offshore wind farm projects in the following aspects?

- **Project acceptance and permitting**
 - Critical
 - Not critical
- **Financing and investment confidence**
 - Critical
 - Not critical
- **Risk mitigation**
 - Critical
 - Not critical
- **Economic benefits for local communities**
 - Critical
 - Not critical
- **Social license to operate**
 - Critical
 - Not critical
- **Long term project viability**
 - Critical
 - Not critical

Section 3: Environmental impact

3.1 Perception and /or awareness questions

26. Do you perceive the environmental impact of floating offshore wind turbines as significant compared to other energy sources or other technologies for the same source?

- *Very significant*
- *Quite significant*
- *Not very significant*
- *No impact*

27. How aware are you of the potential environmental benefits of floating offshore wind turbines compared to other energy sources?

- Very aware
- Quite aware
- Not very aware
- Not aware at all

28. In your opinion, how committed is the FOWT industry to minimising its environmental impact?

- Extremely committed
- Quite committed
- Not very committed
- Not relevant

29. Do you think it's essential to involve the local communities from the beginning of a FOWT project, ensuring they understand both the benefits and drawbacks, to foster better understanding?

- Yes
- No
- Depends on the level of involvement of the local community

Additionally, which type of community involvement do you consider the most effective?

Regular community meetings and updates
Educational workshops and information sessions
Collaborative decision-making processes

Other (please specify)

3.2 Environmental barriers and enablers questions

30. In your opinion, what could be the main environmental impacts and their Intensity (H=high, M=medium, L=low) during the lifecycle of the floating offshore wind turbines?

	Construction	Operation	Decommission
Underwater noise			
Electromagnetic fields			
Water quality			
Impact on birds			
Seabed integrity			
Changes in atmospheric and ocean dynamics			
Mooring Lines and Subsea Cables: Risks to Marine Mammals			
Risk of accidents			
Mining of critical materials			
Disposals of materials			
Cumulative Impact of all planned farms			
Other (please specify)			

31. What are the potential environmental benefits and advantages associated with installing FOWTs and the level of each one (low, medium, high)?

	Low	Medium	High
Creation of marine protected areas from fishing			
Artificial reef			
Reduction in greenhouse gas emission			
Mitigation of climate change effects			
Preservation of land resources			
Protection of marine biodiversity			
Minimisation of air and water pollution			
Other (please specify)			

3.3 Strategies and tools to analyse and minimise the environmental impact

32. In your opinion, how important would it be to standardise procedures and criteria for EIA, mitigation strategies and compensation measures?

- Very important
- Quite important
- Not very important
- Absolutely not

33. What are the main needs/gaps for an effective Environmental Impact Analysis and the relevance of each one? (Low, Medium, High)

	Low	Medium	High
Lack of long term data			
Poor knowledge of deep sea biodiversity			

Insufficient knowledge about seabed characteristics			
Lack of funds to perform accurate analyses			
Availability of pilot FOWTs along with dedicated marine areas for monitoring and testing			
Use of digital technologies			
Creation of multidisciplinary teams and new professional skills			
Other (please specify)			

Section 4: Technical barriers and enablers

Technological barriers

34. How familiar are you with floating offshore wind technologies compared to bottom-fixed technologies?

- Very familiar
- Quite familiar
- Not very familiar
- Not familiar at all

35. What are the key technological barriers currently limiting offshore wind energy deployment in your region? Rank the following technological concerns or challenges in order of importance for developing, operating, and deploying offshore wind energy, particularly floating offshore wind turbines:

- Stability and structural integrity of floating turbines

- Anchoring and mooring systems for floating turbines
- Transmission of electricity from offshore turbines to shore
- Maintenance and accessibility of turbines in remote offshore locations
- Maturity of available integrated design tools for offshore wind
- Development of high voltage dynamic cables for offshore transmission
- Cable connectors (e.g. wet-mate connectors)
- Floating substations for offshore wind farms
- Understanding of coupled environmental impacts from offshore wind
- Other concerns (please specify)

36. What are the main geographical characteristics in your region that limit the impact of technological challenges for offshore and floating offshore wind development?

Technological Enablers

37. Establishing a competitive and innovative supply chain that actively supports and invests in the necessary infrastructure for rapidly achieving offshore wind deployment targets is essential for reaching our Net Zero targets.

- Agree
- Disagree
- Not aware
- Others (please specify)

If agreed, what critical infrastructures are necessary to increase the capacity and capability of the supply chain?

- Logistics (e.g. ports)
- Grid reinforcement
- Standardisation and modularity of components
- Optimisation of installation and operations
- Others (Please specify)

38. What technological solutions or innovations are being developed or deployed to address the key barriers you identified for offshore wind in your region?

39. What are the main challenges or limitations in developing and deploying these technological solutions in your region?

40. Innovation in product design and construction techniques will drive the growth of the floating offshore wind sector. What are the most urgent issues that require R&D investments to enable the sector's growth?

- Surveying
- Manufacture and assembly
- Operation and maintenance methods
- Component and substructure design
- A systematic approach to developing supply chain

41. To what extent do you agree that the scale and location of future floating offshore wind deployments are dependent on supportive government policies, regulations, and industry innovation?

42. How effective do you think the current technological solutions are in addressing the challenges specific to floating offshore wind turbines?

- Highly effective
- Moderately effective
- Slightly effective
- Ineffective

43. To what extent can technological advancements contribute to reducing the overall cost of energy production from floating offshore wind turbines?

- Significantly
- Moderately
- Slightly
- Not at all

44. What role does technological innovation play in advancing the development and deployment of floating offshore wind turbines?

- The key driver for growth and expansion
- Moderate impact on progress
- Minimal influence on development
- No impact

45. Do you believe that technological advancements in floating offshore wind turbines can help address environmental concerns associated with their deployment?

- Yes
- No
- I'm unsure

46. Do you believe the government should financially support the geological survey of the sea bed to install the floating offshore wind turbine?

- Yes
- No (Please specify)

47. What other measures need to be taken to foster the broader growth of the floating offshore wind sector, involving collaboration with other entities to accelerate technology development?

- Data sharing and digitalisation
- Investment in skills gap and resources,
- Collaboration and partnership with international key players
- Other necessary actions (please specify).

Integration of Hybrid Offshore Technologies

48. What types of hybrid offshore technologies (e.g. wave, tidal, floating PV, hydrogen) are being considered or deployed in combination with offshore wind or floating offshore wind in your region?

49. What are the main advantages, disadvantages, and challenges of integrating these hybrid offshore technologies with offshore/floating offshore wind in your region?

50. How do the geographical characteristics of your region impact the feasibility and performance of these hybrid offshore technology systems?

51. What are the key market opportunities and barriers to deploying integrated offshore technology systems in your region to support a net-zero future?

Section 5: Financial barriers & enablers

Perception and /or awareness questions

52. How significant are floating offshore wind farms as an investment opportunity in the renewable energy industry?

- *Highly significant*
- *Moderately significant*
- *Insignificant*

53. How would you rate the perceived level of risk associated with investing in floating offshore wind farms compared to traditional investments?

- *High Risk*
- *Medium Risk*
- *Low Risk*

54. What level of financial return would you expect from an investment in floating offshore wind farms compared to other investment options?

- *Higher financial returns*
- *Comparable financial returns*
- *Lower financial returns*

Redistribution of funds coming from FOWT

55. What should be the top priorities for redistributing funds generated by FOWT within local communities?

- Renewable energy infrastructure
- Job creation and training programs
- Affordable Housing Initiatives
- Environmental conservation and restoration

- Community education and awareness
- Support for SMEs.
- Climate Change Adaptation and Resilience
- Technological Innovation
- Waste Management and Recycling Programs
- Other, please specify

Financial barriers

56. Based on your experience in the development of offshore floating wind projects, Please select the options that represent relevant barriers to investing in FOWT in your country:

- Lack of funding.
- Lack of government support for floating wind farms.
- Lack of communication between developers, marine planners and coastal communities.
- High Levelised cost of energy.
- High manufacturing costs.
- High operating and maintenance costs.
- The current status of floating offshore wind technology (FOWT)
- A well-developed supply chain is needed.
- Availability of ports and installation infrastructures
- Long installation and decommissioning time.
- Negative impact of stakeholders on the timeline of the FOWT construction period.
- Lack of standardisation for FOWT.
- Fluctuation in energy prices and market dynamics.
- High taxes, charges or fees during the implementation phase.

Financial enablers

57. Select the relevant financial incentives or support mechanisms that encourage more investments in offshore wind farms in your country.

- Grants and subsidies
- Low interest loans
- Green bonds and climate funds
- Infrastructure support and co-financing
- Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs)
- Power Purchase Agreements
- Innovation and R&D funding
- Investment tax credits (ITCs)
- Production tax credits PTCs)

- Renewable energy certificates (RECs) and guarantees of origins (GOs).
- Other (please specify)

58. Based on your experience, please select the relevant enablers to invest in FOWT:

- The government provides financial support for FOWT projects to reduce investor risk, such as grants, cheap loans, or favourable long-term electricity purchase contracts.
- Collaboration between the government and any financial institutions to support investment in FOWT.
- Policy support mechanisms such as incentives to lower the levelized cost of energy of FOWT.
- Platforms to share and transfer knowledge and experiences from bottom-fixed wind plants, Oil and gas plants with floating offshore wind plants.
- Government efforts to improve communication between developers, marine planners and coastal communities.
- Government financing reforms to support original equipment manufacturers of FOWT.
- Increase confidence in wind turbine original equipment manufacturers, for example issuing comprehensive warranties.
- Government planned interventions to reduce the high cost of operating and manufacturing FOWT.

Financial solutions and investment:

59. What are the financial instruments offered by financial institutions for developing FOWT projects in your country:

- **Construction loans**, *specifically tailored to cover the costs of constructing offshore wind infrastructure, typically repaid once the project reaches commercial operation.*
- **Term loans**, *fixed-term loans with set repayment schedules, providing financial stability for offshore wind projects.*
- **Bridge loans**, *short-term loans that bridge financing gaps during specific project phases, often repaid when the project secures long-term financing.*
- **Revolving credit lines**, *lines of credit that provide flexibility for offshore wind developers to draw funds as needed during different phases of a project.*
- **Export credit financing**, *financial support provided by export credit agencies to facilitate the export of goods and services related to offshore wind projects.*
- **Green bonds**, *debt instruments issued by financial institutions with proceeds allocated to environmentally sustainable projects, such as offshore wind.*
- **Loan guarantees**, *financial institutions may offer guarantees to lenders, reducing the risk and encouraging investment in offshore wind projects.*
- **Interest rate swaps**, *derivative contracts used to manage interest rate risk, allowing parties to exchange variable interest payments for fixed-rate payments.*

- **Collateralized debt obligations (CDOs)**, securities backed by a pool of debt, including loans to offshore wind projects, often divided into different tranches with varying levels of risk.
- **Subordinated debts**, loans with lower priority in repayment hierarchy, often carrying higher interest rates, providing additional capital to offshore wind projects.
- **Soft loans**, loans with below-market interest rates or more favourable terms, often provided by government-backed financial institutions to support strategic industries like offshore wind.
- **Mezzanine financing**, A hybrid of debt and equity financing, where financial institutions provide capital with the expectation of higher returns than traditional loans.
- Others, please specify

Investment cost and revenues:

60.Based on your knowledge please fill the table below:

Are you aware of the following information about the FOWT sector in your country	Yes/No	If Yes provide an estimate	Annual growth trend (Increasing, Stationary, or Decreasing)
Cumulative investments			
Total revenues			
Fixed maintenance and operating costs			
Variable maintenance and operating cost			
Debt to equity ratio in the FOWT sector			

Section 6: Market barriers and enablers

Market perception and awareness questions

61.How well-informed do you feel about the current market trends and potential growth in the floating offshore wind energy sector?

- Well informed
- Neutral
- Not well informed

62.How would you classify the level of engagement (low, medium, high) in the FOW sector in your country of the following key stakeholders:

	Low	Medium	High
Policy makers			
Investors			
Research community			
Industry			

63. On a scale from 1 to 5, with 1 being 'Very low' and 5 being 'Extremely high,' how would you classify the level of market attractiveness of your country in terms of the following key factors:

	1 - Very low	2 - Low	3 - Medium	4 - High	5 - Extremely high
Market size and growth rate					
Stability and regional competitive environment					
Bankability of renewables (cost and availability of finance, liquidity of transactions market, etc.)					
Strength of local supply chain					
Long-term energy strategy and level of underpinning policy stability					
Market incentives / Policy support mechanisms (FITs, FIPs, CfDs, TGCs...)					

Strategic aspects: cultural, administrative, geographic and economic distance from other markets					

64. In the scenario of large-scale deployment of floating offshore wind, will your country primarily resort to:

- A domestic supply chain
- An international suppliers entry.

65. On a scale from 1 to 5, with 1 being 'Not at all important' and 5 being 'Very Important', how would you rate the importance of the following market barriers occurring in your country?

	1 - Not at all important	2 - Slightly important	3 - Important	4 - Fairly important	5 - Very important
Public concerns or lack of awareness regarding the safety and aesthetics of offshore wind installations.					
Unfavourable regulatory environment and the lack of long-term political frameworks					
Insufficient port facilities and infrastructure for manufacturing, assembly, and maintenance					

High levels of marine traffic, including shipping lanes and fishing activities					
Lack of availability of specialised vessels and equipment					
Environmental Impact and ecosystem concerns					
Issues with social acceptance and support from local communities					
Grid connection challenges					
Competition with established fixed-bottom offshore wind projects					
Complex permitting and approval processes					
Lack of guaranteed market access or secure power purchase agreements					

66. On a scale from 1 to 5, with 1 being 'Not at all important' and 5 being 'Very Important', how would you classify the importance of the following market enablers in your country?

	1 - Not at all important	2 - Slightly important	3 - Important	4 - Fairly important	5 - Very important
Clear and consistent policies that provide incentives, subsidies, and a regulatory framework supporting the development of floating offshore wind projects					
Stable and predictable policy environment with long-term commitments					
Financial incentives and subsidies					
Investments in R&D					
Investments in education and training programs to support the development of a skilled workforce					
Adequate investment in onshore and offshore grid infrastructure					
Collaboration between government entities and private industry					

Proactive and transparent engagement with local communities and stakeholders					
Cooperation with other countries, industry stakeholders, and international organisations					
Policies to promote a competitive market environment and the diversification of energy sources					
Development of infrastructure to support manufacturing and supply chain					

67. On a scale from 1 to 5, with 1 indicating 'Not at all important' and 5 being 'Very Important', specify the importance of the following factors that represents opportunities for a market expansion on FOWT in your country:

	1 - Not at all important	2 - Slightly important	3 - Important	4 - Fairly important	5 - Very important
Relevant previous activity (reduces risk and facilitates market penetration)					
Public support (through both technology-push and market-pull mechanisms)					

Energy resource (significant over a relevant area)					
Infrastructure capabilities (research infrastructures, dedicated facilities and test sites, ports for fabrication, assembly, quick reaction ports, electricity grid infrastructure)					
Specific national research focus on the field					
National targets concerning the share of offshore wind energy in gross final energy consumption					
Public processes such as marine spatial planning in place to facilitate efficient consenting					
Advantageous upcoming electricity market reforms					
“One-stop-shop” platforms					
Partnerships between academia, the public and the private sector to foster innovation (‘centres of excellence’)					

68. In your opinion, what essential policy supports are required to facilitate the development of the floating offshore wind market? Additionally, should tailored standards, certifications, and reform policies be implemented to facilitate the development of the floating offshore wind market?

